

TECHNOLOGY AT CROSSROADS: AN ANALYSIS

Dr. Gayatri Mohanty

Associate Professor, Nalini Devi Women's College of Teacher Education,
Bhubaneswar, Odisha

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Introduction:

Modern world is shaped by technology; it tumbles from crisis to crisis. There are prophecies of disaster and indeed visible signs of breakdown everywhere. Techno-logy, although the product of man, tends to develop by its own laws and principles; and those are very different from those of human nature or living nature. Nature always knows when to grow and when to stop. There is measure in all natural things - in their size, speed and violence. So, the system of nature of which man is a part tends to be self-balancing, self-adjusting and self-cleansing. Technology, on the other hand, recognizes no self-limiting principles in terms of size, speed, and violence. So in the subtle system of nature, the super-technology of the modern world acts like a foreign body and there are innumerable signs of rejection. Modern technology has deprived man of the kind of work that he enjoys most - creative, useful work with hands and brains. It gives him plenty of work of a fragmented kind, most of which he does not enjoy at all.

People have forgotten to differentiate between work and leisure. They are always productively engaged. Everybody relies heavily on mindless entertainment or other drugs, which create much illness. The ideas of competition, natural selection and survival of the fittest, purports to explain the natural and automatic process of evolution and development. Taking these into consideration, can we say that a way of life has emerged that bases itself on materialism? 'More', 'Further', "Quicker, and 'Richer' are the watch-words of present techno-sawy society. They lead us to a limitless expansion on the finite environment.

The Other Face:

On the other hand, technology seems to lighten the burden of work to stay alive and develop his potential. When man first stepped on the moon on July 20th 1969, nearly 2 billion people on earth participated in a historic learning experience. A new technological vocabulary was introduced. A new realization of the worldwide unifying power of multimedia communication was dramatically demonstrated as everyone saw, understood and appreciated the accomplishment of an unprecedented feat through teamwork, co-operative effort for the journey to the moon.

Technology and the Classroom:

School today finds itself with constantly more and more of subjects to teach. The child spends more time in school. No longer can a small head of the Teacher carry all that a student must learn. We must do something drastic to enable us to handle the staggering build up of new knowledge. Teachers who confront over-flooding knowledge view it as a mixed blessing. On the other hand, there is no shortage of opportunities - economic, social and personal. On the other hand, complicated learning and instructional problems accompany such non-copable increases in school population. To face this challenge a changing curriculum needs be introduced.

Effective Technology:

- Effective learning begins with firsthand experiences and proceeds towards more effective and abstract experiences. Thus, a student who has the advantage of reacting to well selected and widely used media and materials can learn more effectively than one who is provided with predominantly verbal information.
- A learner profits most from instructions when he becomes involved through his own interests and desires. A well-chosen educational media present concepts in such a way as to incite interest and stimulate involvement.
- A student who is knowledgeable and whose interests are aroused is better able to perform as a creative, inventive human being.
- The most objective evidence that a learner has accomplished his goal is to be found as one observes and evaluates the quality of the responses.
- She makes to instructions. Observable behaviour shown by the learners after they responded to media instructional opportunity, present tangible evidence that can be measured, evaluated and used by teachers, as the basis for continuous re-planning and improvement.

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